

Public summary
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WP7
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1. Summary of the context and overall objectives of the project

The amount of waste generated by households in the EU-28 was 243 million tons in 2015, which is about 9 % of the overall generation of municipal and industrial waste. Most of waste (63%) derives from construction and demolition, mining and quarrying, but household waste despite being only 9% can generate a high environmental impact if disposed to landfill.

Each person in the EU generated 475 kg of municipal waste every year, ranging from 759 kg per capita in Denmark to 272 kg per capita in Poland and Romania.

It has a very high political profile because of its complex character, due to its composition, its distribution among many sources of waste, and its link to consumption patterns. The management of this waste cost billions for our public budgets. Overall, 26% of municipal waste is still sent to landfill, 27% incinerated and only 47% of municipal waste in EU is composted or recycled. Looking at the already existing local best practices, it is possible to reach 80% recycling.

This means that 80 million tons of recyclable materials are thrown away or 'wasted' annually. Even more may come from the industrial sector.

Among recyclables, biowaste (and especially food waste) is the most sensitive fraction but it is currently separately collected only in a few Member States.

The sector contributing the most to food waste is households (47 million tonnes). About 75% of food waste may be avoidable. Composting would allow to store carbon in the soil, improving fertility and offsetting industrial GHG emissions.

Furthermore, waste management accounted for over 3% of total GHG emissions in Europe (over 100 million tons of GHG).

We need to treat waste as a valuable resource, shifting away from final treatment and disposal models towards a recycling and recovery model, based on the principles of the Circular Economy.

The EU action plan for the Circular Economy and waste framework Directive aims to improve waste management practices, stimulate recycling and innovation in materials management, and limit the use of landfilling. New ambitious goals have been proposed by 2030 to move forward a new management paradigm such as:

- Need to Increase Overall Recycling rate of municipal waste to 70%
- Obligation to introduce separate collection of biowaste aimed at the generation of high quality compost and digestate
- a food waste reduction target of 30% by 2025 and of 50 % by 2030 compared to the 2014 baseline;
- Need reduce landfill to a maximum of 10% of total waste.

To realize the potential of this model we need to improve the waste management systems across European countries.

The aim of Waste4Think project is to meet these challenges testing the effectiveness of new eco-innovative solutions (technological and non-technological) to prevent: waste generation, enhance collection, and increase the treatment, recycling and recovery of high-grade valuable materials from waste.

These Eco-innovative solutions will be developed and tested in real-life environments, 4 urban areas in Europe, the highly industrialized village of Zamudio (Spain) that uses a separated kerbside collection, the residential town of Seveso (Italy) that uses a door-to-door system, the large suburban city of Halandri (Greece) that has at the beginning of the project a very basic waste management system and the high touristic coastal town of Cascais (Portugal) with an underground collection system.

These 4 locations have different levels of industrialization and social, demographic and geographic features, as well as different realities on matters concerning waste management, the project considered 4 of them as a single integrated urban metabolism, opening the way for innovative, systemic approaches, involving the analysis of resource flows within 4 cities.

The consortium in charge of carrying out the initiative is made up of a total of 19 partners from SMEs, public agencies and universities in Spain, Greece, Portugal, Italy, Denmark and Germany.

The implementation of the solutions will have an integrated approach, covering the whole waste value chain through the establishment of a holistic methodology for data

management and particularly focusing on citizen participation to build more sustainable urban areas.

The aim is to demonstrate the value of integrating eco-innovative solutions, economic, social and environmental dynamics, in a way to better understand the socio-economically and gender nuanced patterns of resource use and consumption, and pinpoint drivers of waste-avoiding behaviour, improving in the same way public governance and business models related to waste management moving towards a circular economy model.

The project aims to obtain measurable results with the integration of these solutions across the four pilots:

- Reduction of waste generation (8%),
- Increase of urban waste sorting (20%),
- Waste management costs savings (10%),
- Reduction of GHG emissions (10%)
- Waste diverted to landfill around a 23% of reduction

1.1. Brief presentation of the Work Plan

WASTE4THINK is coordinated by the Institute of Technology DeustoTech from the University of Deusto (Spain) and structured in nine work packages (WP)s to achieve an efficient realization of the project's objectives.

Pilots Planning and execution is handled in **WP1**. The objective of this work package is twofold. On the one hand, this work package contains all the actions to define the requirements and setup the pilots sites. On the other hand, in this WP the impact achieved with the technological and non-technological actions deployed in the pilot site will be monitored.

The main objective of **WP2 "Development of Computer Assisted Integral Waste Management Systems"** is to develop IT tools in order to support waste managers in the operation and planning systems under sustainability criteria. For this, an appropriate waste data management platform will be deployed to retrieve, store and exploit recorded data, optimizing the integral waste management in a holistic way taking into consideration socio-economic variables (including gender dimension), the generation patterns and geospatial information.

These IT tools will provide the building blocks to construct the rest of the solutions of the project allowing to retrieve the information needed and to monitor the impact of the actions implemented. Finally, an incentive planner will be also implemented to foster the adoption of circular economy solutions.

The objective of **WP3 “Implementation of alternatives for the recovery of high-grade materials”** is to demonstrate, within the circular economy context, innovative approaches for waste streams that are currently either handled in non-optimized way or diverted to landfills. In more specific, the main principles of circular economy will be applied upon kitchen wastes, disposable nappies and expired food products providing products of high value and/or energy decreasing thus their diversion ratio to landfills.

The activities within **WP4 “Creation of Innovative Social Actions”** are to:

- Define new social actions to promote prevention and citizen empowerment
- Implement a set of teaching units and serious games to increase the impact of the social actions and foster mutual learning
- Carry out a citizen science activity for the co-creation of innovative eco-design solutions
- Design 3 Apps to foster transparency and citizen engagement

WP5 “Definition of new Economical Instruments” is to set up proper regulations and incentive schemes, at a municipal level, aimed at introducing innovative Pay-as you –Throw ‘PAYT’ systems or other penalty/reward schemes in the most effective way according to the collection scheme to be implemented.

WP6 “Exploitation of Eco-innovative solutions” is in charge of identifying and exploiting the most market ready results in order to introduce the eco-innovative solutions deployed and tested in the project into the market allowing connections among other cities and potential investors interested in the solutions to achieve sustainable urban environments.

The objectives of **WP7 “Dissemination and Communication”** are to:

- Implement an ambitious Dissemination and Communication Plan to set up and manage an effective communication strategy and to guarantee the public coverage of the project results at the pilot level.
- Promote the project at a wider level organizing different events, participating in top level conferences, fostering cooperation among the projects funded within

this call to engage citizen, public administrations, stakeholders, the scientific community and other EU initiatives and platforms.

Knowledge and information transfer through multiple channels and networks will be centrally coordinated and managed by **WP8 “Project Management”**.

Finally, **WP9 “Ethics”** is in charge of the ethical issues that affect the project.

2. Work performed from M14 to the end of the period (M25)

The work performed during the second year of the project per WP, is explained below:

2.1. WP1: Pilots planning and execution

This Work Package covers all the tasks related with the preparation and execution of the pilots. During this period objectives related with the preparation activities have been successfully achieved. Pilots deployment have recently started with the implementation of some social actions and consequently the first results related with decentralized solutions for valorization and reuse of high value resources, educational materials based on innovative teaching units and serious games and tools for citizen science. The following actions have been carried out within this WP in the second year of the project:

2.1.1. Task 1.1. Pilots preparation

This task has been completely fulfilled. The two subtasks that make up this task are explained in their corresponding deliverables. On the one hand, the legal framework analysis, compiled in Deliverable D1.1. (submission November, 28th). On the other hand, the definition of WESTE methodology defined in the Deliverable D1.3. (submission November, 30th).

2.1.2. Task 1.2. Pilots planning

This task has been also fulfilled with the contribution of all partners. The permits needed for the implementation of the actions foreseen in the pilots have been compiled, the databases of best practices in circular economy, economic instruments and prevention actions have been built (Deliverable D1.2.; submission July, 10th), several templates for the Requirement analysis have been completed by all partners (D1.1.) and after building the overall and the particular architecture of the pilots sites, a template was completed to built a draft of the API (D1.1).

Finally, the deployment of the IT developers infrastructure have been completed including the FIWARE nodes (FIWARE Labs), the databases (Mongo, Mysql and CKAN) and different developers environment (Deliverable D2.1.; submission December, 19th).

2.1.3. Task 1.3. Sustainability Modelling

In this task, pilots have retrieved the information needed to estimate their current state of the portfolio of KPIs (D1.3). The model of the waste generation according to the socio-economic characteristics of the municipalities to identify the generation patterns (including gender dimension) and future trends cannot be carried out at this stage of the project due to the lack of historical information. It will be calculated later as more data is collected. The calculation of the KPIs needed to assess the environmental impact of the waste management system will be done as soon as the Long Term Planning tool (R3) reach at least β status as expected (M28).

The different subsystems and activities involved in each pilot site along the project have been also modeled (zero waste events and ecosystems, sustainable local trade, food waste protocol, green procurement, PAYT and sustainable social actions) and particular KPIs for each subsystem have been defined.

2.1.4. Task 1.4. Pilot deployment

Within this task, the deployment and execution of the four pilots have been started. A specific environmental educational programme for each pilot using the different eco-solutions is defined in Deliverable D 4. 1. (submission October, 17th) according to the temporal and geographical distribution timing (GA: Annex II of Part B).

2.1.5. Task 1.5. Pilot monitoring

The monitoring of the actions carried out in the pilots in terms of the sustainability model has been completed during this period until the next Milestone. To this end, pilots have collected the information needed to update the baseline due to inconsistencies found in the data sources Deliverable D1.4. (submission December, 19th). Several templates have been completed to monitor both the status of the development and its validation on field conditions of on the one hand all eco-solutions in terms of the functional requirements implemented and its implementation status in the pilots according to the timing and on the other hand all the sensors to be deployed at the pilots sites (D1.4.).

Moreover, an assessment of the status of the social action plan of the four pilots sites has been carried out, including a detailed description of the status of the implementation of the different strategies, a summary of the actions carried out on every strategy, a qualitative and quantitative analysis of the actions and the updated calendar (D1.4.).

Finally, an assessment of the KPIs defined for the integral waste management has been carried out for Halandri and Seveso, where significant changes in the waste management systems have taken place (D1.4.).

2.1.6. Task 1.6. Pilots results consolidation and lessons learnt

The first book in the Social Briefing Series from the University of Deusto Press have already been finished and is in press. The second book in the serie is being prepared.

2.2. WP2: Development of Computer Assisted Integral Waste Management Systems

This WP encompasses most of the ICT developments to be made. The tasks developed so far have been:

2.2.1. Task 2.1. Sensor Platform

Tasks on the MOBA platform are already fulfilled. All the details can be found in Deliverable 2.5 (submission, November 17th). From now on, MOBA will dedicate the efforts on the FIWARE integration within the Software platform.

FDEUSTO has completed the integration and test of the Truck Data App (Filling level/ locks/ clean points and characterization camera). Furthermore, a second revision (more robust) of the hardware is been made.

The city behavior tracking methodology has been defined. However, the implementation has not started yet.

Finally, due to new legislation, the composting plant monitoring could have not been done.

2.2.2. Task 2.2. Software Platform

In this task, the production environment of the back-end have been deployed. Moreover, the security layer have been defined and implemented.

Additionally, the methodology for the integration of the data from the different components have been defined. Implementation of the different connectors (source to the Context Broker and from there to the history module). Retrieving the data from the relevant stakeholders and process it.

FDEUSTO has completed and tested History and CRUD modules; information can now be stored and consulted with an API. CRUD operation can be made in a atomic way without loss of information in case of communication losses. The dashboard now can access seamless both the Context Broker and the History module. Nevertheless, there are some widgets that are not implemented yet.

Regarding the Green Procurement, its implementation have not started yet.

MOBA has developed the MAWIS web platform in order to include a module to maintain and exploit the information from the Chambers (Waste Locks) installed in the bins. The module include the sections for the Waste Locks, the Keys and the Regions (where the keys belong). Such development process includes the integration with the EMZ (Chamber's electronics provider) platform.

In addition, MOBA has included improvements in the web platform in order to make it more user-friendly and faster. From now on, should there be any other improvements in terms of usability, they will be included within the Waste collection optimization.

2.2.3. Task 2.3. Waste collection optimization

The ECO-Driving monitoring tools have been developed in a new Dashboard within MAWIS together with the Maintenance module for the vehicles.

A new tool for the route planning module has been added. This gives the possibility to add Checkpoints on the route to check whether the trucks fulfill the planning as expected. See Deliverable 2.7 (Submission, December, 19th).

2.2.4. Task 2.4. Long Term Planning

This task is carried out by FDEUSTO and SOFTLINE. In both cases they are improving their platform. In particular:

SOFTLINE has been working on the mid-term planning to be included in GERA. The architecture has been defined: Data bases, optimization planner to determine the human resources, vehicles and activities necessary to do a specific activity of waste collection considering, and the inputs needed. The software is currently being implemented.

FDEUSTO is expanding their long term simulation engine to consider waste collection problems.

- A selection of explicative and predictive models, and optimization methods have been carried out and it been implemented.
- A what-if scenario definition interface have been designed and the implementation is been carried out. Components that can be modified have been selected and models are being built.
- Creation of a set of predefined scenarios for every pilot (baselines) have been built.
- Finally, the implementation of the rest of planning tools are been carried out (Green Procurement Tool, Zero-waste Ecosystem/Event Planner and the Invoice planner).

2.2.5. Task 2.5. Incentive System Planner to Foster Circular Economy

On the one hand, the Technical Documentation report of the Circular Economy Planning Module was released in November, 28th (Deliverable 2.9), which provides functional and technical description of the tool.

On the other hand, a workgroup was held between Aclima, ARS and FDEUSTO to define the attributes for the tool. Once defined, FDEUSTO have started its implementation.

Finally, the Best Practices and new business models based on Circular Economy database is being continuously expanded throughout the project.

2.3. WP3: Implementation of alternatives for the recovery of high-grade materials

2.3.1. Task 3.1. “Biomass product” valorization

The potential exploitation of FORBI as feedstock for alternative valorization processes is still being investigated. All the experimental processes for the valorization alternatives are conducted. The 8 eight valorization alternatives are: gaseous biofuels production (methane, hydrogen and HYTHANE), bioethanol production, alternative fuel in the cement industry, pellets, compost, electricity production via Microbial Fuel Cell technology, Activated Carbon production, Animal Feed. Furthermore, FORBI is being transferred to industrial sites in order to scale up some of the valorization alternatives. In order to provide the suitability of FORBI for all the valorization alternatives, the quality and the quantity is being monitored continuously.

Finally, a set of KPIs and FRs have been developed in order to demonstrate and optimize decentralized innovative management solutions regarding the collection of Household Food Waste, the production of a novel product (FORBI) and the valorization of 8 alternatives (Deliverable D3.1.; submission December, 19th).

2.3.2. Task 3.2. Disposable nappies and expired food product valorization

In the frame of circular economy and having in mind that every waste is a potential raw material that could be further valorized to obtain new products, there are ongoing tests for the treatment of the anaerobic effluent sludge and the production of compost. Bilateral meetings also took place, with researchers, stakeholders and companies in the field of plastics for the valorization of the recovered plastics from disposable nappies.

The last six months, Green Technologies Ltd in collaboration with University of Patras have revised and completed the technical specifications of the new equipment that will

be adjusted to the Waste Treatment Unit (WTU), in order to adapt better to the needs of both nurseries and elderly houses. The pilot-scale unit of the WTU is ready, and testing experiments are being conducted at the moment. Regarding the compost production, a screening test for the parameters that affect its quality has been completed in lab-scale and further investigation for the optimization of the process has been planned as shown in Deliverable 3.3 (Submission, November, 29th).

2.4. WP4: Creation of innovative Social Actions

During the second year of the Waste4Think project, where the five major tasks have been initiated, the primary focus of WP4 has been the generation of the pilots social programme and developing four serious games to support this. The objective of this work package is to foster behavioral change in waste producers.

2.4.1. Task 4.1. Generation of the pilot's social programme

The Social Action Plan was finished in M12. Deliverable 4.1 (Submission October, 17th). A new updated version has been finalized in M22 with a more detailed description of the social actions in each strategy and the monitoring system. Other few modifications have been introduced following the comments made by the reviewers.

Zamudio, Seveso and Halandri are developing their social action plan following the calendar with slight deviations. New actions are being included in some pilots under the umbrella of the current educational strategies and taking into account the results of the actions already done.

Cascais has postponed the start of their communication activities until July 2018 mainly due to some delay in the integration of the ID system to the CityPoints app.

Qualitative monitoring of the social actions has been done in almost all the actions, quantitative indicators has been changed in some cases due to the difficulties of measure.

2.4.2. Task 4.2. Learning materials

At the end of the second year of project, the learning materials have been definitely defined:

- 4 STEAM lessons. Four STEAM lesson have already been released after a collaborative design process with schools in Zamudio and Halandri (The first STEAM Lesson was ready in September 2017). Nowadays, these educational material are being tested in pilot-sites,
- 6 Digital Projects have been discussed and agreed. 2 of them have already developed and validated. These Digital projects are - 1. After the Concert and 2. Where is wastey? The last 4 will be completed in November 2018.
- 4 mobile location-based games. Progress have been made and they will be completed in November 2018.

Detailed description of these modules can be found in Deliverable 4.3 (submission February, 7th).

2.4.3. Task 4.3. Serious Games

Within this task, Serious Games has given priority to Sorting and Eco Design games. In both cases, input from the pilots have been received and, therefore, the prototype has been revised accordingly. It is on track to final pilot deployment in September 2019.

On the other hand, the development of an editor for planning game and virtual city has not been started yet because some variables are still not decided.

Technical documentation of the Serious Games is explained in the Deliverable 4.5 (Submission November, 29th).

2.4.4. Task 4.4. Citizen Science

Within this task, a citizen data survey for Zamudio has been designed, with the help of the municipality. This included the creation of the materials, performing the activity and performing the analysis of the information. The data collected was used in the creation of the baseline of Zamudio pilot.

Additionally, the Learning Analytics KPIs of the sorting game have been defined and a draft of the rest of the games have been made.

Moreover, a survey has been done of the best practices applied in the shops at Halandri made by the vocational school childrens.

Finally, the preparation of a summer working camp on Zamudio has started.

2.4.5. Task 4.5. Implementation of the Apps

Regarding the Apps development, during the second year of the project, discussions with all the pilots sites have been held to agree about the functionalities and the Interfaces of the three Apps. The design documentation of the three Apps is now completed and mock ups of the three apps have already been shown and agreed. See Deliverable 4.11 (Submission February, 7th).

Moreover, it has been working on the backend of the apps and in taking more advantages of the services provided by FIWARE. Also, a tighter integration with the rest of solution is also studied for the Citizen App and with the Local Trade App (in particular, with the citizen observatory and dashboards).

2.5. WP5: Definition of new Economical Instruments

This WP covers all the tasks related with the definition of new economical instruments. During this period the objective regarding the raising of the recycling rate of the pilots has been reached in Seveso, where separate collection rate reached increased from 76% to 81% after PAYT implementation.

About the development of an invoice system, the existing software by Sofline has been used in Seveso, and a new invoicing module is under development for Zamudio. For Cascais, MOBA started the development of the general invoicing module to be used in various cases.

2.5.1. Task 5.1. New PAYT schemes

This task is already finished. The results could be read in D1.2., D1.3 and D2.1.

2.5.2. Task 5.2. Definition of specific PAYT systems on pilots

ARS, SOFTLINE and SEVESO have already completed the definition of its new PAYT regulation that it is already into force since April 2017. To this end, the first PAYT invoices with the PAYT calculation have been sent to citizens on November 2017. The

regulation is being continuously improved after the first months of results. Details of all the actions could be consulted in D1.3.

Some specific meetings have been dedicated to the other municipalities, Zamudio and Cascais (Halandri is not committed to introduce PAYT), to improve their regulation for waste management with a view to include PAYT specific criteria. Moreover, in Zamudio the participative process have started with local traders to validate the new PAYT scheme and also during 2017 both the containers and locks choice and the choice of PAYT parameters were made.

In Cascais, the installation of containers lock is already made and the data flow integrated in municipal app.

2.5.3. Task 5.3. Invoicing integration

The preparation of invoicing module, starting from the outcome of Task 5.1 (Deliverable 5.1, submission February 7th), is in progress. For Seveso, an existing invoicing software (Wintarif) is implemented and based on new parameters decided in the new local regulation as well as with different method of invoice calculation in order to have a flexible software adaptable to different European PAYT systems; it was improved the first invoice with the variable part of PAYT and was sent to citizens of Seveso in the end of November and an app that allows consulting the invoices and retrieving information about citizen behaviour and allows citizens to get access to the bill information or submit issues will be provide in the next months. Moreover, a specific integration into a website will be delivered during 2018. The full implementation for the other municipalities (Zamudio and Cascais) is foreseen by the end of the project.

2.6. WP6: Exploitation of Eco-innovative solutions

In the second year of the project, this work package has focused on fostering collaboration among partners who share foreground developments in order to lay the foundations of solid and lasting partnerships. The work done by tasks has been the following:

2.6.1. Task 6.1. Establishment of the Exploitation Board

From M13 to M24 no specific use of the exploitation board has been done. After the M21 meeting in Halandri, Exploitation Board has been reduced in order to ease the information flow and decision making as it was too big previously.

It was stated that all partners had a representative in the Exploitation Board and now it has been reduced to industrial and those related directly with the exploitation strategy to make it more useful.

2.6.2. Task 6.2. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result

From M13 to M21 the work done was under the scope of 20 different eco-solutions and different forms were sent to partners to keep defining business models per each eco solution. IPR strategy for each result was also drafted. Description of these business models can be found in the Exploitation and IPR report; Deliverable 6.1 (submission November, 30th).

After M21 to M24 all this scheme was changed as PO requested. A global strategy for the integral solution was demanded. For M24 meeting, an exploitation hierarchy was defined.

Figure 1. Exploitation hierarchy of Waste4Think

In addition, the sale concept for the integral solution was defined and agreed with partners involved.

5 main different packages have been defined to tackle the exploitation of the integral solutions. Apart from the main packages, a transversal one has been defined. It consists of those activities that can be integrated with any of the 5 main packages.

For next month's it is expected to send D6.1 explaining this exploitation path.

2.6.3. Task 6.2. & Task 6.3. Identification of key results and functional analysis of each key result & Value innovation analysis

These two tasks have been carried out jointly since both are related to activities that are inherently dependent on each other. The first step has been to detect and confirm which are the results with a clear potential for exploitation and/or commercialization. In this sense, there are already 20 Eco-innovative solutions already stated in the Waste4Think Grant Agreement with significant exploitation potential.

Once identified the exploitable results, the merits of the ideas were assessed and a first screen to determine their overall potential was performed by considering relevant aspects that will be critical for the success or failure of the associated business.

2.6.4. Task 6.4. IPR analysis

The previous work done in the framework of protection of intellectual property will help to define the new map considering new situation after the definition of the new exploitation path

Now, the sale concept with the 6 packages is defined and approved by partners. Every partner has a role in the exploitation strategy and a specific IPR strategy will be selected accordingly to their role. It will help to define the break-down of services offered in each package. A collaboration agreement will be signed between partners included in every package.

2.6.5. Task 6.5. Development of business models, business plans and exploitation action plans

As the exploitation scenario has changed, a total of 6 packages have been defined and development of integrated business models will start as soon as the exploitation path is validated by PO. The idea is to develop one business model for each main package (5 in total) integrating the 6th transversal package in the others.

2.7. WP7: Dissemination and Communication

Communication plays an integral role in keeping a project on task. During the second year of the project most of the effort has been focused on improving the website to integrate the other components that make up the Waste4Think platform and disseminate the progress of the project and the events/ workshops/ conferences in which it has been presented. These are the main activities carried out:

2.7.1. Task 7.1. Elaboration and update of the dissemination and communication plans

Within this task, a new version of the Communication and Dissemination Plan (D7.1) was submitted on November 13th (M18). Minor changes were suggested by the PO in the review of the report which have already been included in the deliverable.

2.7.2. Task 7.2. Creation of common communication and dissemination materials

During last summer, two new dissemination materials were designed for the project: an infographics and four specific flyers have been made in English for each pilot. Furthermore, a set of 100 brochures and a poster printed was delivered to each partner in order to be used as promotional materials at events/ workshops/ fairs/ conferences,...

2.7.3. Task 7.3. On-line tools for communication and dissemination

During this period, the website of the project has been continuously updated with the relevant information of the project.

Work has also been done to increase the community of different social networks which keeps growing, especially on Twitter.

The communication KPIs that were defined at the beginning of the project have been monitored monthly and they have been collected in two versions of D7.2 (the last update on November 2017) to be published at the end of the project.

2.7.4. Task 7.4. Clustering activities

In the update of the Communication and Dissemination Plan, a Clustering Activities Plan was included. In addition, partners are recording their clustering activities carried out by partners to keep track of them.

Furthermore, intensive activity has been made regarding networking. In addition, two new members have been included in the advisory board (Ferrovial and IPWCA) and exploitation activities with DFG - Diputacion Foral de Guipuzkoa and Ingubide have been carried out.

Moreover, we are in contact with PPI4Waste and RETRACE projects. In this line, on October 2017, a delegation of Waste4Think partners participated to the Circular Economy Policy workshop where 5 representatives of each project funded by Horizon 2020 focusing on waste and circular economy gathered to discuss together. There were 4 project funded by call WASTE-6a-2015 – Eco-innovative solutions: (Waste4Think, FORCE, UrbanRec, DECISIVE), two by call WASTE-6b-2015 – Eco-innovative strategies (REPAiR, URBAN WASTE) and one by H2020-CIRC-2016-One Stage (SCREEN).

2.7.5. Task 7.5. Communication campaigns for pilots

Different activities have been carried out addressing citizens, such as social events to explain the project, eco-events with dishwashers or compostable materials,...

Four testimonial videos of the pilots were produced describing the status of each pilot, included in the youtube channel of the project.

2.7.6. Task 7.6. Publications and events attendance

Partners have developed intense activity regarding this task. Different articles, press releases, news,... have been published in different resources. The list of publications and attendance to events is being collected in D7.2 to be published in M42.

2.7.7. Task 7.7. International networking workshop

During the last project meeting in Cascais a workgroup was held to discuss the different possibilities of the International meeting in Italy. Finally, it was decided to celebrate the International meeting Ecomondo 2018, coinciding with the project meeting.

A draft of the programme will be shared with the partners shortly.

3. Pilots status

In this second year of the project, the pilots have progressed carrying out different actions.

3.1. Cascais pilot

During this second year of the project, the pilot of Cascais has been, simultaneously, preparing the communication plan's implementation. In the case of citizens, the approach to users will be directly made with personal contact complemented with informative brochures, online information and participation games. Children will be involved in school activities based on our environmental awareness program and Waste4Think applications. Finally, tourists will be directly contacted as well as their landlords.

Additionally, the "City Points" gamification platform is available for users, a rewards program that encourages good citizenship practices, using an APP to give the opportunity to earn points and with them get products and services. When using the APP, one point is given to a daily use, despite the number of usages, five points if you use 80% of days in a given month and 10 points if recycling rates have improved from baseline.

The introduction of RUB (organic waste) bags has been also carried out in order to further the recycling potential within the household waste.

3.2. Halandri pilot

During this second year of the project, the pilot of Halandri has established a closer relationship with the volunteers in the project due to two main reasons. On the one hand, they provided them with two phone numbers in order to answer possible questions they may have and on the other hand, the creation of two Facebook groups. These are used mainly to transmit news about the project but have gradually evolved into a very vivid community where also ideas and experiences among volunteers are shared. Moreover, a second meeting was held with volunteers in June 2017 to present them the progress of the project and two informative events were celebrated with citizens in general to explain the first results and current status of the project.

In November 2017 a waste analysis took place to a sample of about 10% of the participating households. All the three main waste streams were examined: commingled (green bin), recyclables (blue bin) and food waste (brown bin). We measured: a) the total amount per bin generated by our sample for 12 days, and b) the quality of the sorting. The results show that the population of participating households generate less and sort better than average, and confirm our initial assumptions that this population has much better habits than the general population not only in sorting, but also in prevention.

Regarding the Stem lessons in schools, originally, the plan was to implement the educational actions program in one school of Halandri. However, due to the fact that key teachers in the school were overenthusiastic and supportive of this project, it was decided to upgrade the goals and move along the lines of an educational outline in a second school. One of them, has already begun the implementation. The school has already visited the dryer/shredder unit, has already attended an educational demonstration of the truck with the sensors, and are beginning experiments in composting.

Following with the students and in the framework of the commercial activities campaign, 12 students from the vocational high school participated in a survey regarding environmental and waste management habits of food product shops and restaurants/bars and café.

Finally, during this second year the Halandri pilot has had a lot of coverage in the media especially during the meeting that was held in Halandri with all partners coinciding with the celebration of the demo day and the review meeting by the

commission during which both the mayor of Halandri and some partners of the pilot of Halandri made interviews for several magazines / newspapers and local television channels. Besides, they have participated at several environmental exhibitions and conferences and even nominated for the first prize awarded to the Municipality of Halandri in the "Urban Waste Management" category at VERDE.TEC: 2nd International Exhibition on Environmental Technologies. The list of all the events attendance is being collected in D7.2.

3.3. Seveso pilot

In summer 2017 a new activity started: Eco-events, traditional public festivals with low level of waste production and sensitization of participants, carried out with the support of ARS. Instead of plastic dishes, they used ceramic dishes (washed by a dishwasher); citizen have been sensitized and accompanied to sort waste in the correct way and they have been asked to express their satisfaction with this innovation through a smile totem. Waste collected during festivals have been finally weighted.

In march 2018, INNOVA 21 started the promotion campaign for re-usable nappies in families with new-born and nurseries; in summer 2018 ARS and SEVESO municipality will promote the Virtuous household contest, in which a small number of households will be selected and undergo a very strict monitoring to improve their behavior about waste separation.

Regarding The Funny door to door activity, it is still ongoing. Activities such as social street "dinner with waste", theatre performances, info-points in open-air markets, close to bag dispensers, during eco-events, activity in elderly people centre, oratories (parishes), schools,...are taking place or will take place in a near future in Seveso.

During the last month the PAYT regulation has been slightly modified in order to improve it and to maximize people acceptance. Separate collection rate reached 81% after PAYT introduction, from the already high 77% baseline.

Finally, a new APP by SOFTLINE has been tested for possible future use by citizens to deliver real time information to citizens about their waste generation.

3.4. Zamudio pilot

During this second year of the Project, Zamudio pilot has carried out several activities.

First of all, in July 2017 DeustoTech and Zamudio carried out the first Citizen Science activity in the municipality to map, among others, waste collection facilities, households and local economic activities.

During summer, both the second citizen participation meeting was held in order to make contributions to the Project and the first 'eko-festa' was celebrated, where all the elements used in the traditional people's meal were put aside for compost manufacturing.

Another advance in the framework of the project has been the introduction of two Smart lorries to the fleet of urban solid waste collection trucks in Zamudio. These vehicles are equipped both with a weighing system and with a route tracking one, and will thus gather data to work on establishing optimal collection routes.

Regarding dissemination activities, the Zamudio pilot in the framework of Waste4Think was presented at the Basque Ecodesign Meeting (BEM) 2017, one of Europe's most important ecodesign meetings with more than 30 attendees.

Following with the idea of Zamudio of doing surveys to the citizenship to know their habits of separation of the domestic waste and recycling, the last survey was made by call to 350 citizens from October to November 2017 to calculate the baseline.

Several social campaigns have been carried out such as a candle workshop in Zamudio's school made with waste cooking oil and the celebration of the 'Arimen gaba', a basque traditional celebration similar to Halloween.

In this period the third citizen participation meeting has also been celebrated, on this occasion, to work on the design of the PAYT system.

In the last period of the second year, Zamudio has installed definitive bins aimed at collecting used nappies, as well as rubbish bins for different kinds of waste.

Finally, Food storage container campaign was launched which rescues surplus food coming from collective and professional catering services and distribute it amongst a dozen local families.

4. Some pictures

Figure 2. The 'PAYT' tax model, under debate in Zamudio

Figure 3. Reusable nappies campaign in Seveso

Figure 4. Students from Halandri visit University of Patra's Waste Treatment Unit

Figure 5. Communication campaign at Cascais to encourage citizens to participate in the project

Figure 6. Participation of Deustotech at Bilbao "Scienc Fair

Figure 7. Participation of ARS Ambiente at #wasteinprogress

Figure 8. Demo day in Halandri

Figure 9. `Eko-festa` in Zamudio

Figure 10. MOBA participation at Smart City Expo World Congress

Figure 11. SOFTLINE, Legambiente and ARS Ambiente participation at Ecomondo

Figure 12. ACLIMA participation at CONAMA local

Figure 13. Halandri participation at #WasteEng18

Figure 14. Waste4Think workshop at Green Week partner event in Cascais

Figure 15. BCN participation at BIOMETA 2018